

MODERN FICTIONS. SUBALTERN REALITIES.

A SENSITIVE CARTOGRAPHY OF TENSTA'S HOUSING

Bodies / Periphery / Domesticity / Aesthetics / Identity

Arquitectura Subalterna

Desde el entendimiento de la periferia esp como laboratorio de realidades extremas, se establece como caso de estudio el suburbio de Tensta –Estocolmo–, lugar donde se visibilizó, tras las revueltas de 2013, la precaria situación de un barrio diseñado según los dogmas del racionalismo.

En este contexto, el joven rapero Adam Tensta y una familia de inmigrantes, son tomados como representantes de las nuevas formas de relación y acción que los grupos subalternos practican con el ambiente construido. El principal objetivo de esta investigación es analizar -mediante precisas cartografías- las nuevas identidades y estéticas de unas viviendas donde objetos emocionales, sensaciones y pieles se tornan en verdaderas espacialidades. Arquitectura Subalterna busca visibilizar la distancia existente entre la ficción del Movimiento Moderno y la dura realidad de la periferia.

eng From the understanding of the periphery as a laboratory of extreme realities, the Stockholm suburb of Tensta, which after the 2013 riots showed the precarious situation of a district designed through rules of rationalism, has established itself as a case study.

In this framework, the young rapper Adam Tensta and a family of immigrants are taken as representatives of the new forms of relation and action of subaltern groups with the built environment. The main target of this line of enquiry is to analyse -through precise cartographies- these new identities mainly reflected in the aesthetics of houses, where emotional objects, sensations, and skins become the real spatialities. Thereby, *Arquitectura Subalterna* aims to visualize the distance between the fiction of the Modern Movement and the harsh reality of periphery.

-Cartography of Adam's Tensta House-
by Arquitectura Subalterna

-Cartography of family of immigrants in Tensta-
by Arquitectura Subalterna

This Reality-Fiction-Displacement takes place in Tensta's district; an area in the outskirts of Stockholm which had been a military training ground since 1907. But in 1962, because of the housing shortage in the Swedish capital, the government decided that a territory such as this had to become an inhabited fiction. A fiction designed under the ideology of Modern Movement and the economic resources of the 'Million Programme' - a demanding state-led project that built roughly one million of houses in Sweden - between 1965 and 1974 - that made Tensta one of the most conflictive ghettos in the current Stockholm.

People began to move to Tensta in 1967, the functional design seemed to have done its work: an urban layout clean, clear, ordered and 'democratic'. But the lack of infrastructure, significant leisure areas, and opportunity spaces, fostered an early exodus of people. Only inhabitants - mostly immigrants - with low incomes and therefore unable to afford to move, remained. Thus, Tensta began to become consolidated into a ghetto full of people at risk of social exclusion. Such situations remained out of public eye for decades until May of 2013 when several riots broke out in Stockholm periphery. Tensta was one of the 'hot spots' of such upheavals. Once more, reality overcame fiction.

In this framework, we aim to unveil the distance created between a fiction based on a rationalistic ideology, commonly the so-called 'Modern Movement' or 'International Style, and an extreme reality represented by subaltern inhabitants who suffer the consequences of this modern fiction. Is the Modern Movement a fiction? Yes. Its urban and architectural design is understood from functionalist ideas that take as reference reductionist pattern such as Le Modulor. Modulor only takes into account the measures and behaviour of a white 'superman' who is 1,83 tall with an athletic figure. It is a fiction because it is not only possible to inhabit from one dimension - reason - but rather from multiplies one, like sensation.

These complex and diverse realities realities are depicted through two cartographies. One is starring Adam Tensta, a famous black rapper who won the 2008 Grammy Award for best Hip-Hop album, born and raised in the neighbourhood that is both his artistic surname and his debut album ('It's a Tensta thing'). In Tensta, the young people who are marginalised by the system have created their own 'neighbourhood aesthetics' where all the small narratives are recognised and appreciated. The second cartography makes visible the domesticity of an Arabic family

where space is understood through sensitive dimensions.

The houses that embrace these contemporary and unpredictable domestic forms, were designed to accommodate the Swedish family stereotype of the 1970s: four white, blue-eyed and blond-haired individuals (father, mother, son and daughter), who rejected any approach that deviated from the norm. Faced with these fictitious and archaic domesticities, Adam's house is a case of daily resistance reflecting a much more complex, individual and extremely real world.

How does a successful young rapper live in a house from the Modern Movement? How do these affections become visible in new forms of domesticity? Approaching these questions is only possible through the surfaces that wrap and decorate the current homes. Surfaces that in Tensta are understood as skins. The skin, in Paul Valery words is 'the deepest thing there is', and it is full of memories and meanings for their inhabitants. Analysing how the house is decorated, and putting value in these new identity forms are new and pertinent contexts of action and architectural representation.

The houses of Tensta are decorated mostly by emotional objects and skins, creating atmospheres far removed from the white purist walls. Persian carpets, clothes as exotic as they are banal, graffiti or shower curtains, are elements used to reinforce identity in a completely foreign construction. Moreover, an immaterial, sensitive and ephemeral spatial dimension has to be recognised. For instance, the particular smell of oriental foods, the use of incense or simply the steam of a hot shower can change the perception of any room. Tensta's subaltern inhabitants do not need patterns to configure their space because they are guided by their own emotions, feelings, and aesthetics.

Arquitectura Subalterna is a radical research group formed by Víctor Cano Ciborro, José Javier Cullen, José de Andrés and Ana Sabugo, which promotes an architectural approach from affections, identities, and sensations of the bodies that inhabit the space. Their case studies problematize real situations from cartographies which reveal the spatial relations of rebel bodies against dominant narratives. Their work has been recognized in Oslo Architecture Triennale 2016, The Biennale of Venezia 2016, Future Architecture 2017, Pugliarch 2017, Kosovo AF 2017 and XX Chile Bienal 2017. Contributor in this article: Isabel Story www.arquitecturasubalterna.com